

Knowledge, Attitudes, Practices, and Misconceptions on COVID-19 among Students of Tertiary Institution in Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to investigate the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and misconceptions related to COVID-19 among students at Imo State University, Nigeria. The COVID-19 pandemic has posed unprecedented challenges worldwide, including among university students in Nigeria. A total of 194 valid questionnaires were analyzed, representing diverse age groups, genders, faculties, and years of study. The results revealed that the majority of respondents (63.5%) were aged 18-20, with good knowledge of COVID-19 (95.8%) and its symptoms and mode of transmission (89.18%). However, some misconceptions were noted, with a significant number believing in conspiracy theories. Students demonstrated positive attitudes by adhering to social distancing measures (74.36%) and avoiding social gatherings (88.83%) during the pandemic. Nevertheless, the practice of physical distancing was less consistent (22.35%). The pandemic had a substantial negative impact on students' academic performance (86.36%), but online learning was prevalent (94.18%). The study recommends continuous health education, addressing misconceptions, and implementing clear guidelines for preventive practices on campus to create a safer environment during health crises.

Keywords: COVID-19, Knowledge, University students, Imo State

INTRODUCTION:

Emerging and reemerging diseases possess a global challenge to public health (Gao, 2018). The novel coronavirus disease popularly called COVID-19 which has its origin in Wuhan city, China, has rapidly spread across most borders infecting people throughout the world. It is known to present with symptoms such as fever, dry cough, breathlessness, sore throat, recent ageusia (complete loss or absence of the sense of taste), as well as anosmia (complete loss or absence of the sense of smell), muscle pain, headaches, and rashes. In severe cases, patients may progress into acute respiratory distress, multiple-organ dysfunction which may result in death. Some of the infections are also asymptomatic. The disease affects all ages. However, it has been suggested with evidence that two groups of individuals have an increased risk of getting a severe form of the disease. These include people with underlying comorbidities and the elderly. The World Health Organization (2020) reiterates that everyone must protect his or her self to protect others. COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in the mortality of thousands of humans across the globe. The infection has spread to over a hundred countries

prompting the WHO to declare it a pandemic in March, 2020. As of September 4, 2020, there have been 26,121,999 confirmed cases of the disease, including 864,618 deaths worldwide. The first case in Nigeria was reported on February 27, 2020, and as of April 27, 2020 (two months after), there were already 1337 confirmed cases in the country with 40 deaths (Zhong et al, 2020). As of September 5, 2020, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) reported 54,905 total confirmed cases with 1054 deaths affecting all the states of the nation including Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The deaths included health workers, patients with underlying medical conditions, and pregnant women. However, since the first case was reported in the country, the number of infections has been increasing. Apart from the morbidity and mortality associated with the virus, there have been serious social and economic implications on the country. To mitigate this health, social, and economic burdens, governmental and non-governmental organizations have embarked on educating the public on ways to prevent the transmission of the virus. Gatherings of fifty people and above were suspended while all civil servants below the level of an assistant director were asked to work from

home (Olapegba et al, 2020). The presidential task force on COVID-19, in late March 2020 launched several containment plans which included shutting the national borders as well as placing the country on lockdown. However, there has been a gradual easing of the lockdown in Nigeria and the Federal Government on September 3, 2020, announced the third phase of the easing. International flights, amusement parks, gyms, cinemas, and event centers have now reopened, while educational institutions and the national youth service corps orientation camps are currently preparing to follow suit. If this is not properly managed, it could lead to a serious resurgence in the cases of COVID-19 in the country. The best way to reduce and stop transmission is to be adequately informed with regards to the virus, the symptoms, mode of transmission, and preventive measures (Olapegba et al, 2020).

Understanding the attitudes and practices related to COVID-19 among students is essential for promoting behavior change and adherence to preventive measures. By exploring students' attitudes towards the virus, we can identify potential barriers or misconceptions that may hinder compliance with recommended guidelines. This knowledge can inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at addressing these barriers, promoting positive attitudes, and fostering behavior change that aligns with public health recommendations. This study specifically focuses on students from Imo State University, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. By conducting research within a specific local context, we can gather data that is relevant to the specific challenges, cultural norms, and social dynamics of the university community. Overall, this study is justified as it contributes to the understanding of the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and misconceptions related to COVID-19 among students from Imo State University. The findings can inform evidence-based interventions, educational campaigns, and policies aimed at promoting accurate knowledge, positive attitudes, safe practices, and dispelling misconceptions, ultimately contributing to the overall control and prevention of COVID-19 within the university community and beyond.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Area:

The study area is Imo State University, Owerri in Owerri North Local Government Area Imo State, Nigeria. Imo State University was established in 1981 by the old Imo State Government, comprising present-day Imo and Abia States. It is located 5°30'28"N 7°02'26"E on the map and it is 3¹/kilometers from Orji still in Owerri North Local Government area. Imo State University (IMSU) is a coeducational higher education institution. Imo State University (IMSU) offers courses and programs leading to officially recognized higher education degrees such as

bachelor degrees in several areas of study including Arts, Biological Sciences, Engineering, Education, Medicine etc. The study is conducted in the university via Faculties (Faculty of Physical Sciences, Biological Sciences, Medicine, Arts, Humanities etc).

Study Population:

The study population includes 200 students of Imo State University, Owerri. Imo State.

Data Collection and Processing:

The research design that was adopted in this research study was the descriptive survey design. Descriptive survey is a method of collecting information by interviewing or administering a questionnaire to a sample of individuals. It can be used to collect information on people's attitudes and opinions, on a variety of education or social issues. Structured questionnaires were prepared and administered to Individuals that resides in the study area.

Validity Test:

Validity tests for questionnaires will ensure that the questions effectively measure what they're intended to assess. Content validity will confirm that the questions comprehensively cover the topic. Criterion validity will involve comparing questionnaire results to an established standard. Construct validity will ensure that the questions capture the underlying concept accurately. Convergent validity will examine correlations with related measurements, while divergent validity will assesses lack of correlation with unrelated measurements. These tests collectively will verify that the questionnaire produces reliable and accurate data, enhancing the quality of research outcomes.

Date Analysis:

Collected data were inputted and analyzed with statistical software IBM SPSS Statistics for Window, Version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, N.Y., USA). Frequency, percentages, mean, and standard deviation (SD) were presented in tables at univariate level of analysis. Pearson's Chi-square and logistic regression were used to determine the association between outcome and independent variables at bivariate and multivariate levels of analysis, respectively (variables were included in the regression Fmodel using a p-value cut off of <0.2). The level of significance was set at 5%.

RESULTS:

Demographic Information Table 1 shows that out of 200 questionnaires distributed both digitally and physically; only 194 can be referred to as valid. 6 was not properly filled. The majority of respondents (63.5%) were 18-20 years old, with a fairly even distribution across other age

groups ranging from 18 to 23 year and above. Female students accounted for the largest proportion (53.6%) of respondents, followed by males (44.3%), and a small percentage (2.1%) preferred not to disclose their gender. The Faculty of Engineering had the highest representation (28.4%), followed by the Biological Sciences (20.6%) and Medicine (18.0%). The Faculty of Arts comprised 15.5%, while other faculties accounted for 17.5%. The 200 level had the highest representation (33.5%) among respondents, followed by the 300 level (28.4%), the 400 level (21.6%), and the 500 level (16.5%). Knowledge about COVID-19 (table 2). The majority of the students (95.8%) reported that they know about COVID-19, while a smaller number (7) responded "No," and a few (2) were uncertain ("No Idea"). Similarly, a significant number of students (89.18%) reported that they know the symptoms and mode of transmission of COVID-19, while some (7.73%) were not aware, and a few (3.09%) were unsure. The symptoms of COVID-19, including fatigue, cough, fever, shortness of breath, and loss of taste and smell, were mostly known to the students (86.08%). Social media was the most common source of information on COVID-19, followed by newspapers and radio. Table 3 presents the attitudes of students towards COVID-19. Most students (74.36%) reported obeying the social distancing measures imposed by the government.

Additionally, a significant number of students (88.83%) stated that they stopped going to church and social gatherings during the pandemic. However, a smaller number of students (65.73%) reported noticing any special cases during the COVID-19 pandemic. Only a few students (29.94%) mentioned that they went to the hospital to get tested for COVID-19. Practices during COVID-19 Pandemic (table 4 shows that most students reported always wearing masks in public areas (17.11%), frequently practicing hand hygiene (25.69%), and sometimes maintaining physical distancing (22.35%). Table 5 presents the extent of misconceptions about COVID-19 among students. The majority of students (98.86%) were aware that there is a virus called COVID-19. However, some students (19.88%) believed that COVID-19 is a way to depopulate the world, and others (26.43%) thought it is a wrath from God to mankind. Table 6 illustrates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' education. A significant number of students (86.36%) reported that the pandemic negatively affected their academic performance. However, most students (94.18%) mentioned that there was online learning during the pandemic. Regarding the support provided by the university after the pandemic, a majority (59.16%) of students indicated receiving sufficient support.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age(yrs)		
18-20	127	63.5
21-22	57	29.3
23 and above	10	5.2
Gender		
Male	86	44.3
Female	104	53.6
Prefer not to say	4	2.1
Faculty/Department		
Engineering	55	28.4
Biological Sciences	40	20.6
Medicine	35	18.0
Arts	30	15.5
Others	34	17.5
Year of Study		
200 level	65	33.5
300 level	55	28.4
400 level	42	21.6
500 level	32	16.5

Table 2: Knowledge about COVID-19

Question	Yes (%)	No (%)	No Idea (%)	Mean (SD)
Do you know about COVID-19?	185(95.8)	7(3.63)	2(1.03)	1.92 ± 0.25
Do you know the symptoms and Mode of Transmission?	173(89.18)	15(7.73)	6(3.09)	1.86 ± 0.35

Symptoms of COVID-19 include fatigue, cough, fever, shortness of breath, and loss of taste and smell?	167(86.08)	17(8.76)	10(5.15)	1.79 ± 0.42
Sources of information?				
Social media	143(73.71)	30(15.46)	21(10.88)	1.65 ± 0.49
Newspaper	116(59.79)	48(24.74)	30(15.46)	1.43 ± 0.54
Radio	95(49.22)	62(32.06)	37(19.17)	

Table 3. Attitudes towards COVID-19

Question	Yes (%)	No (%)	<i>Mtan ± SD</i>
Did you obey the social distancing imposed by the government?	145(74.36)	49(25.13)	1.62 ± 0.49
Were there any special cases you noticed during the COVID-19 pandemic?	117(65.73)	63(35.39)	1.30 ± 0.58
Did you stop going to church and social gatherings during the pandemic?	159(88.83)	21(11.74)	1.81 ± 0.38
Did you ever go to the hospital to get tested for COVID-19?	58(29.94)	136(70.06)	1.06 ± 0.66

Table 4: COVID-19-related Practices

Practice	Always (%)	Often (%)	Sometimes (%)	Rarely (%)	Never (%)	N/A (%)	Mean±SD
Wearing a mask in public areas (e.g., classrooms, libraries)	56(17.11)	74(22.59)	43(13.15)	12(3.66)	3(0.92)	6(1.83)	3.32±1.12
Practicing hand hygiene (e.g., washing hands, using hand sanitizer)	84(25.69)	66(20.24)	40(12.25)	4(1.22)	0(0.00)	0(0.00)	4.15 ± 0.75
Practicing physical distancing (e.g., maintaining a distance of 1 meter or more)	34(10.43)	60(18.40)	73(22.35)	17(5.20)	7(2.14)	3(0.92)	2.91 ± 1.26

Table 5: Misconceptions about COVID-19

Misconception	Yes (%)	No (%)	No Idea (%)	<i>Mtan ± SD</i>
Was there any virus called COVID-19?	190(98.96)	3(1.56)	1(0.52)	1.98 ± 0.16
COVID-19 is a way to depopulate the world?	42(19.88)	143(67.77)	9(4.27)	1.20 ± 0.40
COVID-19 is a wrath from God to Mankind?	60(26.43)	116(51.10)	18(7.96)	1.43 ± 0.54

Table 6: Impact of COVID-19 on Education

Question	Yes (%)	No (%)	No Idea (%)	Mean± SD
COVID-19 Pandemic negatively affected academic performance?	165(86.36)	24(12.57)	5(2.62)	1.86 ± 0.35
Was there online learning during the pandemic?	178(94.18)	9(4.76)	7(3.70)	1.97 ± 0.25
Did the university provide sufficient support after the pandemic?	113(59.16)	70(36.65)	11(5.76)	1.54 ± 0.48

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and misconceptions related to COVID-19 among students at Imo State

University, Nigeria. The study involved 194 valid respondents, representing various age groups, genders, faculties/departments, and years of study. The results shed light on the students' understanding of COVID-19

and their adherence to preventive measures during the pandemic. The majority of students demonstrated good knowledge of COVID-19, with 95.4% indicating awareness of the disease. This finding aligns with previous studies that have reported high levels of awareness of COVID-19 among university students (Akanbi et al., 2021; Olum et al., 2020). Such awareness is crucial for the effective control of the disease and the implementation of preventive measures. Students displayed positive attitudes towards COVID-19 preventive measures. A significant proportion of respondents (74.36%) reported obeying social distancing measures imposed by the government, indicating a high level of compliance with public health guidelines. Similarly, 88.83% of students stated that they stopped going to church and social gatherings during the pandemic, reflecting a responsible and cautious approach to prevent the spread of the virus. The study revealed positive practices related to COVID-19 prevention among students. The majority of students reported consistent mask-wearing in public areas (17.11%) and frequent hand hygiene practices (25.69%). However, maintaining physical distancing was observed less consistently (22.35%). These findings are consistent with previous studies that have reported variations in COVID-19 preventive practices (Iwunze, 2023; Abay et al., 2021; Olum et al., 2020). Addressing the factors influencing these practices, such as perceived susceptibility and self-efficacy, is essential for promoting consistent and effective preventive behaviors (Olum et al., 2020). The study identified some misconceptions about COVID-19 among students. While the majority (98.96%) were aware of the existence of COVID-19, a notable number believed that COVID-19 is a way to depopulate the world (19.88%) or a wrath from God to mankind (26.43%). These misconceptions highlight the importance of accurate information dissemination and health education to combat misinformation and promote correct understanding of the disease (Alzoubi et al., 2020; Olum et al., 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted students' education, with 86.36% reporting negative effects on their academic performance. However, the majority (94.18%) reported the existence of online learning during the pandemic, indicating efforts by the university to continue education amidst the challenges posed by the pandemic. Moreover, 59.16% of students acknowledged receiving sufficient support from the university after the pandemic. These findings underscore the importance of flexible and adaptive educational strategies during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic (Dwivedi et al., 2021). Overall, the study provides valuable data on students' knowledge, attitudes, practices, and misconceptions related to COVID-19. The findings highlight the need for continuous health education and awareness campaigns to improve knowledge and promote

appropriate preventive behaviors among university students. Additionally, the study emphasizes the significance of providing necessary support to students during and after health crises to mitigate the impact on their education.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and misconceptions related to COVID-19 among students at Imo State University, Nigeria. Overall, the majority of students demonstrated good knowledge and positive attitudes towards COVID-19 preventive measures. However, some misconceptions were identified, indicating the need for accurate information dissemination and health education. The study highlights the importance of consistent COVID-19 preventive practices, especially in maintaining physical distancing. Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, the university's efforts to provide online learning and support to students were noteworthy. Nevertheless, addressing the impact of the pandemic on education remains crucial.

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